

The role of JAK/STAT signaling pathway in Systemic Sclerosis

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INTRODUCTION

Systemic sclerosis (SSc) is a rare multisystem connective tissue disease in which inflammation, fibrosis, vasculopathy and autoimmunity are the principal features leading to diverse organ-based injuries (1). Immune activation is thought to be an early event, with circulating and tissue activated CD4+ T-cells, production of T helper 2 (Th2) cell-derived cytokines (interleukins 4, 10 and 13) and subsequent skin infiltration by macrophages. Differentiation of T helper 17 (Th17) lymphocytes may also be an important process in SSc, promoting fibrosis (2, 3). Gourh and coworkers showed in their research that IL-6 and TNF- α were significantly elevated in SSc patients with disease duration between 0 and 10 years, with no difference compared with healthy controls for disease duration of more than 10 years. In contrast, levels of interleukin-10 (IL10), interleukin-5 (IL-5) and interferon- γ (IFN- γ) were significantly increased in later stages of the disease (>10 years), compared with healthy control (3).

IL-4 stimulates collagen synthesis in fibroblasts by several mechanisms including utilization of the Janus tyrosine kinase (JAK)-1, JAK-2 signaling pathway and by induction of TGF- β 1 and connective tissue growth factor (CTGF) synthesis (4, 5, 6).

THE JAK/STAT SIGNALING PATHWAY

The Janus kinase/signal transducers and activators of transcription (JAK/STAT) pathway is one of a handful of pleiotropic cascades used to transduce a multitude of signals for develop-

ment and homeostasis in animals, from humans to flies. In mammals, the JAK/STAT pathway is the principal signaling mechanism for a wide array of cytokines and growth factors. JAK activation stimulates cell proliferation, differentiation, cell migration and apoptosis. These cellular events are critical to hematopoiesis, immune development, mammary gland development and lactation, adipogenesis, sexually dimorphic growth and other processes (7). Disrupted JAK/STAT signaling may lead to variety of diseases, such as skin conditions, cancers and disorders affecting the immune system. There are 4 JAK proteins: JAK1, JAK2, JAK3 and TYK2 (8). JAK contains a FERM domain (approximately 400 residues), and SH2-related domain (approximately 100 residues), a kinase domain (approximately 250 residues) and a pseudokinase domain (approximately 300 residues) (9). There are 7 STAT proteins: STAT1, STAT2, STAT3, STAT4, STAT5A, STAT5B and STAT6 (8). The binding of various ligands, usually cytokines, such as interferons and interleukins, to cell-surface receptors, causes the receptors to dimerize, which brings the receptor associated JAKs into close proximity. The JAKs then phosphorylate each other on tyrosine residues located in regions called activation loops, through a process called transphosphorylation, which increases the activity of their kinase domains. The activated JAKs then phosphorylate tyrosine residues on the receptor, creating binding sites for proteins possessing SH2 domains (10). STATs then bind to the phosphorylated tyrosines on the receptor using their SH2 domains, and then they are tyrosine-phosphorylated by JAKs, causing the STATs to dissociate from the receptor. These activated STATs form heterodimers or homodimers, where the SH2 domain of each STAT binds the phosphorylated tyrosine of the opposite STAT, and the dimer then translocates to the cell nucleus to induce transcription of target genes (9). STATs may also be tyrosine-phosphorylated directly by receptor tyrosine kinases, but since most receptors lack built-in kinase activity, JAKs are usually required for signaling (8).

ROLE OF JAK/STAT SIGNALING PATHWAY IN SYSTEMIC SCLEROSIS

Dees and coworkers showed in their article that increased activation of JAK-2 was detected in the skin of patients with SSc, particularly in fibroblasts. The activation of JAK-2 was dependent on transforming growth factor β (TGF β) and persisted in cultured SSc fibroblasts. Inhibition of JAK-2 reduced basal collagen synthesis selectively in SSc fibroblasts, but not in resting healthy dermal fibroblasts. Inhibition of JAK-2 prevented the stimulatory effects of TGF β on fibroblasts. Treatment with TG101209 (selective JAK2 kinase inhibitor) not only prevented bleomycin-induced fibrosis, but also effectively reduced skin fibrosis in TSK-1 mice (11). Several other studies showed that patients with limited cutaneous SSc (lcSSc) with

pulmonary arterial hypertension (PAH) overexpressed IL-13RA1, ICAM-1, CCR1, **JAK2** and MCR1 (12, 13, 14). Pendergrass and coworkers showed in their article that patients with lcSSc and PAH, had higher levels of circulating monocyte related cytokine mediators (TNF α , IL-1 β , IL-6, ICAM-1) and vascular injury markers (VEGF, VCAM-1, VW Factor), and their PBMCs (peripheral blood mononuclear cells) exhibited increased expression of mRNA for ICAM1, IL-1 β , JAK2, IFNGR1, IL-13R α 1, tissue inhibitor of metalloproteinase (TIMP)-2, delta-aminolevulinic synthase 2 protein (ALAS2), CCR1, and AIF1akt (14). Fibrogenic effect of IL-6 in fibroblasts is brought about by binding of IL-6 to soluble IL-6 receptor (IL-6R) by a JAK1 and STAT3-dependent mechanism that is mediated through Gremlin-1, which utilizes TGF- β type 1 and 2 receptors and the TGF- β signaling pathway dependent on Smad3 that leads to CI (type I collagen) gene expression, but is not dependent on TGF- β protein (15).

Fujita and coworkers published a case report of an 71-year-old woman with rheumatoid arthritis complicated by systemic sclerosis and type 1 diabetes that were resistant to multiple disease-modifying antirheumatic drugs. A treatment with baricitinib (JAK1/2 inhibitor) was introduced. After baricitinib administration, the disease activity of her rheumatoid arthritis was attenuated from the early stage of treatment, and the effect was maintained for up to 52 weeks. In addition, the skin sclerosis in systemic sclerosis showed an improvement. Regarding the influence on type 1 diabetes, the required daily dose of insulin and hemoglobin A1c (HbA1c) levels decreased. Authors concluded that baricitinib was effective for systemic sclerosis and type 1 diabetes, as well as for rheumatoid arthritis, for up to 52 weeks (16). You and coworkers analysed the effectiveness of tofacitinib for the treatment of refractory skin thickening in diffuse cutaneous systemic sclerosis (dcSSc). Data from 10 patients with dcSSc treated with tofacitinib (5 mg twice daily) were analysed. A total of 12 dcSSc patients treated with intensive conventional immunosuppressants were selected as the historical comparator group. A clinically relevant response was defined as a decrease in the modified Rodnan skin score (mRSS) of >5 points and $\geq 25\%$ from baseline. Clinical indicators were compared between the two groups to evaluate the effect of tofacitinib. The mRSS significantly improved the first month after tofacitinib treatment, with a mean change in the mRSS of -3.7 (95% CI -5.52, -1.88; P = 0.001) and greater than the comparators at 6 months [-10.0 (95% CI -14.74, -5.26) vs -4.1 (95% CI -7.49, -0.73), P = 0.026]. Tofacitinib-treated patients had a significantly shorter response time than the comparators (P = 0.015 by log-rank test), with overall response rates of 20% (2/10) vs 0% (0/12) and 60% (6/10) vs 16.7% (2/12) at 1 and 3 months. Authors concluded that tofacitinib may be as effective as or even better than intensive conventional immunosuppressants, with a quicker and higher response rate in refractory dcSSc patients with progressive skin thickness (17). Kyriakou and coworkers published a case report of a 58-year-old woman with diffuse SSc who developed axial spondyloarthritis (axSpA). The

patient had a 10-year history of SSc and was treated with tocilizumab before the onset of lower back pain. The diagnostic evaluation included MRI that demonstrated bone marrow oedema in the sacroiliac joints, the HLA-B27 was positive, and given the inflammatory features of her back pain, she was diagnosed with axSpa. The biologic agent was switched into etanercept with an improvement of the back pain, but the patient had a relapse of her skin manifestations. Authors decided to treat these coexisting conditions concurrently with tofacitinib, which led to symptom improvement, and concluded that tofacitinib might be a novel therapeutic agent in the management of SSc and axSpA (18).

CONCLUSION

JAK1/JAK2 inhibitors might be useful in the treatment of systemic sclerosis, but more clinical research is mandatory.

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